

Policy brief – Deliverable 2.3

Employment diversity in Europe

Intersectionality and data gaps

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European Labour Markets Under Pressure –
New knowledge on pathways to include persons
in vulnerable situations

Title: Employment diversity in Europe: Intersectionality and data gaps

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PATHS2INCLUDE is a 3-years research project funded by Horizon Europe that investigates the multi-dimensional aspects of discrimination, policies that could reduce inequalities and promote social inclusion in European labour markets and risk factors of vulnerability that may arise in the future of work. The research focuses on three key labour-market processes: recruitment; career paths; and early exit from working life, giving particular attention to labour-market participation at the intersection of gender, ethnicity, age, health, disability and care responsibilities.

1. Introduction

Labour market vulnerability across Europe arises from the interplay between individual characteristics, such as gender, health status, age, education, and caregiving responsibilities, and broader contextual factors, including national welfare regimes, regional labour market structures, and global crises such as the COVID-19 pandemic. These characteristics operate intersectional: they do not merely add up but interact in ways that generate unique and compounded vulnerabilities.

Intersectionality provides an analytical lens for understanding how individuals experience labour market disadvantage. It draws attention to how multiple individual characteristics combine to produce configurations of vulnerability, shaping people's opportunities, constraints, and outcomes in the labour market. This perspective highlights the need to move beyond single-axis approaches in order to capture the complexity and diversity of lived experiences.

At the same time, structural and institutional contexts mediate these individual-level characteristics. Labour market vulnerability is not a fixed or inherent trait but is produced and shaped by broader societal conditions. National welfare regimes, public policy infrastructures, regional economic structures, and social norms all play a role in defining who is at risk and why. Moreover, these systems can either mitigate or exacerbate the disadvantages faced by persons in vulnerable situations, depending on how they are designed and implemented.

The PATHS2INCLUDE project explores these dynamics and underscores the need for intersectional, context-aware, and data-informed policy responses. The findings show how current data limitations, and the lack of harmonised, disaggregated, and comprehensive information prevent the development of effective, evidence-based policies. The following sections present a summary of some of the key findings from the project and a set of potential policy actions aimed at strengthening inclusive labour market governance across Europe.

2. Main findings

2.1. Persistent gaps in data availability

One of the main barriers to understanding and addressing labour market vulnerability is the lack of detailed and harmonised data across European and national surveys. This limitation affects both the quality of research and the capacity for evidence-based policy design.

Many surveys include relevant information on groups at-risk of labour market vulnerability (see Table 1), but important gaps remain on disability, caregiving responsibilities, race or ethnicity, and gender identity. Even so, sample sizes for groups at the intersection of multiple vulnerabilities (e.g., women with health-related limitations in rural areas) are often too small to allow for meaningful analysis. In addition, varying definitions and indicators across national and regional datasets hinder comparative research and the evaluation of policies.

Table 1. Summary of at-risk groups that can be identified in European and international databases

Database	At-risk groups													
	Persons with disabilities	Low SES	Low educational level	Gender identity	Sexual orientation	Mothers, lone parents	Carers	Physical appearance	Older persons (>60)	Young people (<30)	Migration background	Race or ethnicity	Religious Affiliation	Citizenship
EU-SILC	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
EU-LFS	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
AES	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
EHIS	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
HBS	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
EWCS	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
EQLS	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
ESS	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
LIS	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
EU LGBTI	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
GGS	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
Life in transition	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
SHARE	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
WVS	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
ECS (enterprises)	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
WBES (enterprises)	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
CVTS (enterprises)	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
SES (enterprises)	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■

■	The at risk-group can be identified
■	The at-risk group can be partially identified
■	The at-risk group cannot be identified

Source: Valls et al. (2024)

Without comprehensive, harmonised, and disaggregated data, researchers and policymakers cannot fully assess the barriers faced by persons in vulnerable situations, nor identify which policy interventions are most effective in addressing labour market exclusion.

2.2. Labour market vulnerability is context-dependent

Labour market disadvantages are not only linked to individual characteristics but also shaped by institutional and policy contexts. For example, women with children may experience different outcomes depending on the parental leave entitlements and childcare infrastructure available in their country or region. Likewise, older workers are more likely to face early labour market exit in places where retirement systems lack flexibility or where training opportunities are scarce.

For instance, PATHS2INCLUDE research (Valls et al. 2025) shows that in countries with higher health expenditure as a share of GDP, individuals with health-related limitations are more likely to remain in the labour market. In both 2019 and 2022, increased public health spending was significantly associated with improved labour market attachment and a smaller gap between those with and without health-related limitations. This suggests that national investment in health can mitigate structural barriers.

Additionally, the findings indicate that in contexts with low health expenditure, older adults with tertiary education were more likely to remain employed after the pandemic. This illustrates how context and individual resources interact to shape outcomes. Without adequate institutional support, only those with higher education could overcome health-related or age-related disadvantages.

Despite these revealed differences, further comparative analysis remains limited because few context-level indicators can be linked to individual data, restricting the assessment of how regional or national conditions shape labour market vulnerability.

Understanding the influence of context is essential. Only with this knowledge, policies can be designed to effectively address specific challenges in particular regions or countries.

2.3. Labour market vulnerability is intersectional

Disadvantages in the labour market rarely occur in isolation. Rather, they are shaped by overlapping and mutually reinforcing systems of exclusion. A young migrant woman with care responsibilities and health-related limitations may not simply face more barriers than others. The combination of characteristics is likely to create specific challenges and barriers to labour market entry, stability, and progression she will encounter, a type of exclusion arising from the intersection of her vulnerabilities.

This intersectional nature of disadvantage leads to complex labour market trajectories, often characterised by instability, low income, and long-term exclusion. Standard policy responses that target a single characteristic (e.g., gender or health-related limitations) are unlikely to address the compounded nature of the challenges faced by many individuals.

Intersectional vulnerability requires not only more nuanced data but also policy frameworks capable of recognising and responding to this complexity. Without them, policies risk overlooking the experiences of those who do not fit neatly into singular categories.

Consistent with previous research on intersectional disadvantage in the labour market, Valls et al. (2025) find that women with health-related limitations living in households with dependents face the strongest disadvantage in labour market attachment. Their exclusion is not simply additive because caregiving roles amplify the impact of health-related limitations in gendered ways. The analyses also show that education can buffer some intersectional disadvantages: individuals with health-related limitations and tertiary education had higher labour market attachment than those with lower education. For women and men alike, higher education reduced the negative effect of disability and helped narrow the gender gap, especially in the post-pandemic context.

3. Policy recommendations

Based on Valls et al. (2024) and Valls et al. (2025), we outline possible policy actions for consideration, grouped into three pillars:

Pillar 1. Better evidence

- **Strengthen inclusive and intersectional data collection**

Expand the coverage of European and national surveys to include variables on disability status, caregiving responsibilities, migration background, ethnicity, and gender identity. This information must be collected in a harmonised and systematic way to enable cross-country comparisons and support intersectional analysis. At this moment, much of this information is limited in Eurostat surveys, such as the *European Union Statistics on Income and Living Conditions* (EU-SILC) and the *European Union Labour Force Survey* (EU-LFS), and Eurofound surveys, including the *European Working Conditions Survey* (EWCS) and the *European Quality of Life Survey* (EQLS).

- **Ensure statistical visibility of at-risk groups**

Increase the sample size of underrepresented populations (e.g., Roma communities, people with non-binary gender identities, or migrants in informal work) in European and national data collections to ensure sufficient sample sizes for analysing multiple and overlapping disadvantages. Currently, many datasets lack the information to identify persons in vulnerable situations such as young migrant women with disabilities or racialised single fathers, limiting evidence-based policymaking.

- **Expand and strengthen longitudinal data structures**

Create new longitudinal data infrastructures and reinforce existing ones (e.g., EU-SILC) by incorporating retrospective modules, expanding sample sizes, and improving panel retention. These improvements are essential to understanding how labour market vulnerability emerges, accumulates, and changes over time. In parallel, promoting open and timely access to anonymised microdata will facilitate independent research, support rigorous policy evaluation, and foster innovation in labour market policymaking.

Pillar 2. Tailoring policy to diversity

- **Adopt intersectional policy frameworks**

Move labour market policies beyond single-issue approaches. Interventions targeting gender, disability, or age in isolation often overlook the combined effects of multiple forms of disadvantage. Policies should be designed with an intersectional lens, taking into account how characteristics such as migration background, ethnicity, age, and caregiving responsibilities interact in different labour market measures such as recruitment, training and upskilling, workplace accommodation, and wages. This also means acknowledging that multiple vulnerabilities can compound discrimination and exclusion from the labour market and ensuring institutional capacity for intersectional and cross-sectoral coordination in labour market policies.

- **Promote context-sensitive policy design**

Recognise that regional differences in institutions, infrastructure, and labour market conditions are essential for effective policy. Subnational governments should be empowered with the resources, autonomy, and data needed to design measures that reflect local realities. Linking microdata to regional indicators allows policymakers to assess which structural factors reduce or intensify labour market vulnerability, and to tailor interventions accordingly.

Pillar 3. Tracking progress

- **Improve regional comparability and contextual linkages**

Include consistent NUTS-2 or NUTS-3 identifiers in all relevant datasets to enable meaningful subnational analysis. These regional markers are essential for linking individual-level data to contextual indicators (e.g., childcare provision, training opportunities, or public spending) to better understand how regional and local contexts shape labour market vulnerability.

Strengthening these linkages will allow researchers and policymakers to assess how local and regional conditions influence labour market outcomes, to identify territorial disparities, and design more targeted and effective interventions.

- **Foster inclusive evaluation and monitoring**

Labour market outcomes should be regularly monitored using disaggregated indicators (e.g., gender, age, disability, migration background, and caregiving status). Systematic disaggregation is essential to make visible the situations of groups that are often overlooked in aggregate statistics. Such monitoring relies on the longitudinal and inclusive data infrastructures outlined in Pillar 1. By doing so, policymakers can ensure that no workers are left behind in progress tracking, and that targeted interventions can be designed and evaluated effectively.

4. Conclusion

In conclusion, reducing labour market vulnerability in Europe may require a shift in how we collect data, design interventions, and evaluate outcomes. This policy brief suggests moving toward approaches that recognise the intersecting nature of disadvantage and the importance of regional and institutional context. By investing in more inclusive data systems, promoting tailored and context-aware labour market policies, and ensuring that evaluation frameworks capture the realities of at-risk groups, policymakers can develop more effective responses that leave no one behind. Findings from the PATHS2INCLUDE project point to the value of strengthening the evidence base and policy capacity needed to address the diverse challenges faced by workers in vulnerable situations across Europe.

5. References

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